

RNA22 v2 results

Results have been computed and are shown below. If there are no results shown, it means your chosen parameters yielded no results.

Note: The p-value represents the likelihood that the target site loci is random. That is, a lower p-value represents a greater chance that the loci contains a valid MRE

miR Name ▲	transcript name ◆	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol) ◆	heteroduplex	p value ▲
hsa_mir_18a_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1161	-13.50	AACTCCGCCAGCT-TCAGCACCTTC : GATAGACG--TGATCTACGTGGAAT	3.91E-2
hsa_mir_19b_1_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2404	-15.60	AAGTGAAGCAGACTACAAGACC : : CGACCTACGTTGGACGTTTGA	1.35E-1
hsa_mir_19b_1_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2676	-13.40	TCTGCCCTGCTGGCCGGCACAATC : : CGAC-CTACGTTGGACGTTTGA	1.33E-1
hsa_mir_19b_1_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	3884	-20.70	GCTGGTACTGCATGCACGCAATGCT : : CGACC--TACGTTGGACGTTTGA	3.29E-1
hsa_mir_222_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1569	-15.80	CAGCCCTACAGATGGTGGTCTGAG : : TCCTAGATGT--GACCG--ATGACTC	7.85E-2
hsa_mir_222_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2325	-13.80	AGCTTCTGCAC--CCAGTGAA : : TCCTAGATGTGACCGATGACTC	1.89E-1
hsa_mir_222_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2630	-12.20	AG-TGCTGC-CTCCTCTGCTGAC : : TCCTAGATGTGA-CCGATGACTC	1.35E-2
hsa_mir_31_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	3110	-16.20	AGCCTCTGCCA--ATCTGGCCG TCG-ATACGGTCGTAGAACGGA	2.85E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	113	-17.70	CAGAACACAGCTGCCTCCAGCCT : : : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	1.02E-2
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	202	-14.90	CTACCCAGGACCTGTTCTGCCT : : : : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	7.17E-2
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2283	-17.40	GGCGATTCCACCGAGTGCTCCAACCT TCGTAACGTTGGCT--AG-GGTTGGA	2.49E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2678	-14.90	TGCCCTGCTGGCCGG-CACAATCA : : : TCGTAACG-TTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	1.33E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2901	-14.70	GACGTGGTCAACGAGATGCCAGGCA : : TCGTAAC-GTTGG-CT--AGGGTTGGA	1.35E-1

miR Name ▲	transcript name ↕	leftmost position of predicted target site ↕	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol) ↕	heteroduplex	p value ↕
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	3103	-12.40	AG-ATTAGAGCCTCTGCCAATCT : : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	2.85E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	4005	-12.40	AGT-TCCAGACACTCCCAAGCA : : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	6.56E-3
hsa_mir_9_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	381	-14.60	CTGGACAGCAAGA--CCCAGAGC : AGTATGTCGATCTATTGGTTTCT	9.3E-2
mir_21_3p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	163	-14.50	ACTACCC--CGACAAGGTGTC TGTCGGGTAGCTG-ACCACAAC	3.06E-1
mir_21_3p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	1568	-22.70	TCAGCCCTACAGAGTGGTGGTG TGTCGGG-TAGCTGACCACAAC	7.85E-2
mir_21_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	2874	-12.90	ACAGCAAGCGCCCTGGGAAAGCTG : : : : AGTTGT-AGTCAGACT-ATTCGAT	9.97E-3
mir_21_5p	MQ287666.1 Sequence 16 from Patent WO2021214204	3187	-13.50	AGGGCTACCACCTGATGAGCTT : : AGTTGTAGTCAGACTATTCGAT	3.38E-1

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